

HOW TO USE SYNONYMS EFFECTIVELY IN ARTICLES?**Bozorboyeva Iroda Qutbiddin qizi**

The student of Navai State Pedagogical Institute

Sadikova Dildora Nizomovna

assistant teacher of Navaiy State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This paper aims to show the result of analysis of utilizing synonyms in articles which can help to colour the written information. Besides, reading articles can also help to enhance not only intellectual thinking but also improve vocabulary range for EFL learners. Therefore, Reading articles can be combined with vocabulary structure as well.

Keywords: Synonyms, near-synonyms, affect, effect

English language is widely spoken and as a lingua- franca language it has its own priorities to learn it. Even though different accents and pronunciations around the world but written form is the same in globe. One of them can be articles. Nowadays, reading articles also helps to enhance overall English reading and writing skills as well vocabulary range. Newspapers are an excellent way to brush up on current events and practice your English. They provide numerous columns for news, trends, personal life and relationships, the stock market, sports, and other topics.

Knowing what's going on in the globe thanks to being informed on all the news. Particularly in the modern world, where we have all at some point monitored the increasing number of coronavirus cases, which occur roughly every four to five hours.

It is always better to have a decent conversation with others rather than sitting like an idiot, isn't it? Reading newspapers will also increase your knowledge. Reading is always seems to be boring and unattractive theory among most of the students. Thus, to be provided some fun for it , you can combine reading and learning vocabularies from scientific articles.

Students, researchers, and academic staff often face challenges in using synonyms effectively. There is no time or reason to learn new words, let alone understand how to use synonyms correctly. Also, there are many ways to learn new topic vocabularies. Some people think that articles are not necessary for the reader or learner. This is because they do reading passages of each assignment. I, however, believe that articles will always help us to improve our reading skills, speaking skills, collect new topic vocabularies and how to use synonyms effectively. First of all, an article is selected, and all tasks are performed in sequence. Through reading articles and news you can learn a lot of topic vocabularies with synonyms about various topics. For the first time, it is so difficult, but over time many topic vocabulary and synonyms are covered and new words are hardly encountered.

Everyone can agree that the English language richness is more than comparing with other European languages. Learning how to use synonyms effectively can provide the reader with colorfulness both written and oral speech. Hence, choosing a right word for each situation might be utterly confusing when you avoid making expression more arid and repetitious. As we know, the word synonym in the linguistics can have exactly meaning or nearly the same as another word or phrase in one language. Synonyms may be any part of the speech, on condition that both words must belong to the same part of speech:

Noun: chance and opportunity

Verb: attend and go

Adjective: gorgeous and magnificent

Adverb: very and highly

Phrasal verbs: pass away and kick the bucket

Prepositions: by and next to

Negative prefix : un- and im- , unhappy and impolite

In linguistics the term **synonymy** has ambiguity of the words. Words that have the same meaning are said to be synonymous which they can be in one particular function. Synonyms with exactly the same meaning belong to a same or denotational

sememe while these with incisively similar meanings share a broader denotational or connotational sememe and thus overlap within. As Cruise established the scale of the synonymy: absolute synonymy, cognitive synonymy and near-synonymy. The last one is more common in writing. Near synonyms are lexemes whose meaning is relatively close or more or less similar. The senses of near-synonyms overlap to a great degree, but not completely. [Murphy, 2003, 155] Moreover, unlike cognitive synonyms, near-synonyms can contrast in certain contexts:

He was killed, but I can assure you he was NOT murdered, madam.[Cruse 2000;159]

Near-synonymy is regularly found in dictionaries of synonyms or thesauri where most of the terms listed under a single dictionary entry are not considered to be cognitive synonyms (e.g.govern direct,control, determine, require). [Maja2009:19] It is generally accepted that writing in English is a difficult process for English as a foreign language learners , it is not surprising that errors in writing are found as an unavoidable part of foreign language learners writing. Inferences are frequent in discourse of the English learners. They are eager to replace every word of the task by choosing synonymy. It would be better for learners to analysis more words and meanings relating to collocations, near synonyms in theausarus meanwhile practicing the writing.

When we try to use the synonyms the surface meaning seem to be similar exactly but we should draw attention there is a slight difference on account of tone .The tone of communication shows you what you are going to say and provide with variety meanings of the word. In discourse communication using synonyms is vital like “blood for human body” . They can color the speech in different way to provide with essential meaning to emphasize the word meaning in certain tone.

The most common examples are pretty and handsome as two different forms which have the same sense. However, pretty collocates with female and handsome collocates with male Different words that are similar in meaning usually differ for a reason: woman can be used for person rather than female ; and extended are only

synonyms in one usage and not in others (for example, a long arm is not the same as an extended arm).

To support the idea that we analyzing the synonyms in writing , I can present the article from the magazine an article **New Scientist | 4 March 2023 /36 page** <https://www.newscientist.com/issue/3428/> about Earth transformation untold story.

To enhance the vocabulary range first of all you should read this article, you must underline vocabularies and synonyms. Matching the meanings in Vocabularies are in bold. Changed words which is like (influence) are synonyms. Marriam Webster dictionary helps to identify to the exact meaning or similar meanings of the word usage. Let's take some of the examples from the article :

“How much of an influence has climate had on human history? How early in our existence did we **begin to affect the environment**? Can a sudden drought really cause a society to **collapse**? And what does "collapse" mean? These are just some of the questions that historian Peter Frankopan tackles in his ambitious new book, *The Earth Transformed*. Frankopan is best known for his 2015 book *The Silk Roads*, which argued that human history was heavily influenced by **commercial routes** that spanned southern Asia. This time, his subject is the role of the environment in history: how the rise and fall of **empires** has been influenced by **volcanic eruptions, storms and shifts** in the climate, and how, in turn, societies have disrupted the ecosystems in which they exist.

The book is part of a genre that includes author Jared Diamond, of *Collapse and Guns, Germs, and Steel* fame. If anything, Frankopan is more ambitious than many other such writers, **running from** prehistory through the origin of farming and writing to the present. Frankopan also **aims for** a global account by including case studies from every continent.

Any such **sweeping account** will inevitably include some arguable claims. For instance, Frankopan is too accepting of the Toba **bottleneck hypothesis**: the notion that the eruption of the Toba **supervolcano** in Indonesia 74,000 years ago caused **global cooling, devastating ecosystems** and nearly **driving humans extinct**. This idea

has been dismissed by many **palaeoanthropologists(2)** for the lack of evidence of widespread **ecological disruption** at the time or of any impact on prehistoric humans. For me, the sections on prehistory were the **weakest**.

But, once Frankopan gets into recorded history, he hits his **stride**. As he works his way from the deep past to the present, he highlights how societies have come into **conflict with** nature and how those conflicts **played out**. Some of the examples, like the fall of the Maya **elite**, will be familiar. Others aren't yet widely known... ." [**New Scientist | 4 March 2023 /36**]

The best way to explore the vocabulary usage and learn new synonyms can be reading articles. Hence, I wanted to distinguish the vocabularies that unfamiliar to me and analyze the synonyms from the article.

➤ **Influence- impact- effect** - the power to have an effect on people or things, or a person or thing that is able to do this: For instance: bad/good influence on Helen's a bad/good influence on him.

have influence - over He has a huge amount of influence over the city council.

exert influence- Christopher hoped to exert his influence to make them change their minds.

under the influence of- At the time she was under the influence of her father.

➤ **Ambitious- aspiring- vainglorious** - **having a strong wish to be successful, powerful, or rich:**

an ambitious young lawyer -He's very ambitious for his children (= he wants them to be successful).

➤ **Societies- public- association** - **a large group of people who live together in an organized way, making decisions about how to do things and sharing the work that needs to be done. All the people in a country, or in several similar countries, can be referred to as a society:**

a classless/multicultural/capitalist/civilized society These changes strike at the heart of British/American/modern society.

➤ **Continent- restrained- guarded - one of the seven large land masses on the earth's surface, surrounded, or mainly surrounded, by sea and usually consisting of various countries:**

the North American continent to the continents of Asia and Africa

➤ **Palaeoanthropologist- scientist - an expert who studies or works in one of the sciences:**

a research/nuclear scientist

➤ **Widespread- extended - existing or happening in many places or among many people:** Minnesota has experienced widespread flooding.

➤ **Evidence- fact- material - one or more reasons for believing that something is or is not true:** evidence of The police have found no evidence of a terrorist link with the murder.

[+ to infinitive] There is no scientific evidence to suggest that underwater births are dangerous.

[+ that] Is there any scientific evidence that a person's character is reflected in their handwriting?

give evidence Several experts are to give evidence on the subject.

circumstantial evidence There is only circumstantial evidence against her, so she is unlikely to be convicted.

documentary evidence Campaigners now have compelling documentary evidence of the human rights abuses that they had been alleging for several years.

fresh evidence Fresh evidence suggests that the statement had been fabricated.

forensic evidence The traces of petrol found on his clothing provided the forensic evidence proving that he had started the fire deliberately.

all the evidence All the evidence points to a substantial rise in traffic over the next few years.

➤ **Deep past- antecedent - someone or something existing or happening before, especially as the cause or origin of something existing or happening later:**

Charles Babbage's mechanical calculating engines were the antecedents of the modern computer.

➤ **Highlight- illuminate- emphasize - o attract attention to or emphasize something important:**

The report highlights the need for improved safety. be highlighted in The spelling mistakes in the text had been highlighted in green.

What is the differences between **affect and effect?**

Affect vs. Effect: Should I Use Affect or Effect?

Affect and effect are similar words with comparable meanings and pronunciations, so it's little wonder that so many speakers of American English confuse the two. Here we will provide a quick guide for using the two words correctly.

a) Use the verb effect when you mean bring about or brought about, cause or caused. Example: He effected a commotion in the crowd.

Meaning: He caused a commotion in the crowd. Example: She effected a change in procedure. Meaning: She brought about a change in procedure.

b) Use the noun effect when you mean result. Example: What effect did that speech have?

c) Use the verb affect when you mean to influence rather than to cause.

For example: How do the budget cuts affect your staffing?

d) affect is also used as a noun to mean emotional expression. Example: She showed little affect when told she had won the lottery.

Affect is usually a verb, and it means to impact or change. Effect is usually a noun that you would use to indicate the result of a change. Because "affect" and "effect" are homophones (words that sound alike), they are often confused.

Using **affect** or **effect** is always confusing. The basic difference between affect and effect is:

- **affect** is typically used as a verb that refers to an action.
- **effect** is typically used as a noun that refers to an outcome.

In other words, an action can affect something. The result of that action is an effect. Affect is what's happening; effect is a result.

affect in a Sentence

As we've established, affect is often used as a verb, as in the following sentences:

I was tired from traveling, but I tried to not let it affect my performance at the convention.

As inspiration to save more money, think of how losing your income for six months or longer would affect your family.

Effect in a Sentence

Once again, in many cases, effect is the result of action, as shown in these examples:

Shining blue light on the snowfall created an interesting effect.

Giving Greg a huge bonus had the effect of motivating him.

Vocabulary and synonym are available, which in turn we can use all kinds of writing and speaking tasks. I believe that words are really helpful. It can be prevents the reuse of words.

In conclusion, Synonyms are tent to be the most important part of the written and speaking speech. Exact the same or almost same meaning should be differentiate according to word usage in context. In addition to this one get information from reading articles as well improving vocabularies for foreign language learners.

References:

1. F.R. Palmer " Semantics " second edition 1981, p-96;
2. Sadikova Dildora Nizomovna. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR) - Peer Reviewed Journal Volume: 7 | Issue: 4 | April 2021|| Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2013 || SJIF Impact Factor 2021: 8.047 || ISI Value: 1.188
3. New Scientist | 4 March 2023
36,<https://www.newscientist.com/issue/3428/>

4. Sadikova Dildora Nizomovna. SJIF Impact Factor 2021: 8.013| ISI I.F.Value:1.241| Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2016. ISSN: 2455-7838(Online) EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) Volume: 7 | Issue: 1 | January 2022.
5. <https://www.merriam-webster.com>
6. <https://www.GrammarBook.com>
7. <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/affect-vs-effect>.